

DESIGN OF FORENSIC METADATA SYSTEM TO SUPPORT THE DIGITAL INVESTIGATION PROCESSES

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Abstract— The action of cyber crime is increasing day by day, as a comparison of the increasing number of syber crimes that have been revealed by the police. In various cyber crime cases that occur today, there is digital evidence that can help officers in uncovering a criminal case. One of them is through information embedded in various kinds of digital evidence content such as documents, messages, images, sounds, videos and other digital evidence content, which is called file metadata. So far, forensic analysts in analyzing digital evidence have focused on finding preliminary evidence whose content has been deemed relevant for investigative purposes. Currently, many forensic analysts are still searching manually for files related to initial evidence. However, when the files to be related or correlated are in different drives or folders and the number of files will certainly be a tough challenge for forensic analysts in finding and analyzing digital evidence. So that in this research a solution will be proposed through the development of a forensic metadata system prototype to identify the metadata file characteristics in detail and analyze the correlation of the initial evidence file metadata with related or relevant files in the context of the investigation using metadata parameters. With this research, it is hoped that it can contribute to or contribute to investigators, especially forensic analysts in identifying and analyzing related digital evidence files through a metadata-based approach.

Keyword: *Metadata File, Forensic, Digital, Design System, Analysis of Result*

I. INTRODUCTION

So far, forensic analysts in analyzing digital evidence have focused more on finding preliminary evidence whose content has been deemed suitable for investigative purposes. It is possible that there are files related to the contents of the initial evidence. With a metadata-based approach, there are still a lot of manual searches for files related to initial evidence. However, when the files to be related or correlated are in a different drive or folder and the number of files will certainly be a tough challenge for forensic analysts in analyzing the digital evidence [1].

Metadata is structured information that describes, describes, locates, or makes it easier to retrieve, use, or manage an information source. Metadata is often called data about data or information about information [2]. Metadata is information that is embedded in a file, which contains a description of the file. This metadata contains information about the contents of a data that is used for file or data management purposes later in a database [3]. Metadata can be defined as "data about (spatial) data", contains information

about the characteristics of the data and plays an important role in the data exchange mechanism. Through metadata information, it is expected that data users can interpret the data in the same way, when users see the spatial data directly. The metadata document contains information that describes the characteristics of the data, especially its content, quality, condition and method of collection. Metadata is used to document spatial data relating to who, what, when, where, and how spatial data is prepared [4].

As the diversity of digital evidence in the investigation process continues to grow with advances in technology, we are facing newer digital devices, more files with various file extensions, these developments are profitable, and at the same time provide new opportunities for technological crimes. information. In various cases of syber crime that occur today, with the presence of digital evidence that can help investigating officers in uncovering a criminal case. One of them is through information embedded in various kinds of digital evidence content such as documents, messages, images, sounds, videos and other digital evidence content, which is called file metadata [1].

So that in this study we will propose a solution through the development of a forensic metadata system prototype to identify the metadata file characteristics in detail and analyze the metadata correlation to search for related files in the context of the investigation using predetermined metadata parameters. So that it can increase the findings of evidence and make it easier for forensic analysts to analyze digital evidence and the relationship of digital evidence. With this research, it is hoped that it can contribute to or contribute to the investigator forensic analysts in analyzing related files or the correlation of digital evidence through a metadata-based approach.

The purpose of this study is to produce a forensic metadata system prototype to support investigators in identifying and analyzing the relationship between digital evidence.

The output of this research is a prototype that will be useful for forensic investigators / investigators in the police. This forensic metadata prototype will be especially helpful for investigators in identifying and analyzing correlations of digital evidence. Increase the findings of digital evidence and make it easier for investigators to uncover a cyber crime case.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Several previous studies related to forensic metadata were used as references in the writing of this study.

In a study conducted by S. Raghavan (2013), said that to simplify the process of analyzing the relationship of digital evidence, in his research, he built an analysis system called AssocGEN using metadata to determine associations between artifacts, user files, logs and identify metadata to classify and determine correlation. between artifacts and groups of related artifacts [5].

Subsequent research analyzed the BitCurator project to develop an extensible strategy for converting and combining digital forensic metadata into the archive metadata scheme and focusing on metadata generated by the open-source Digital Forensic (DFXML) tool [6].

In his research build an AssocGEN analysis system using metadata to determine the association between user file artifacts, logs, and disposal of network packets and identify metadata to group and specify correlations between artifacts and related artifact groups [7].

Ezz El-Din Hemdan & Manjaiah D.H (2015) also in their research conducted a forensic analysis approach for digital objects such as digital photos and documents. These objects contain important metadata that investigators can use to help investigate cloud-related crimes. Metadata can also be used by attackers to carry out illegal activities so there is a serious need to protect metadata as it provides investigators with reliable information to carry out forensic investigations [8].

A. Spore (2016) conducted a study entitled "Report Information from ProQuest" which aims to analyze metadata, namely linking data with other information, users accessing it, file directory where it is stored, last copied, and so on. [9].

PR Kumar et al (2016) conducted a study entitled "Location Identification of the Individual based on Image Metadata," to verify metadata associated with images and tracking using the GPS feature based on GPS Altitude, GPS Latitude, GPS Longitude and GPS position using the Geo tagging feature [10].

From some of the literature reviews above, this research will propose a solution through the development of a forensic metadata system prototype to identify file metadata characteristics in detail and analyze the metadata correlation to find related files in the context of investigation using predetermined metadata parameters. So that it can increase the findings of evidence and make it easier for forensic analysts to analyze digital evidence and the relationship of digital evidence. With this research, it is hoped that it can contribute to forensic analysts, especially in analyzing related files or correlating digital evidence through a metadata-based approach.

III. BASIC THEORY

A. Application Tools

The tool used to build forensic metadata is netbeans. Netbeans is an Integrated Development Environment (IDE) application based on Java from Sun Microsystems that runs on Swing. Swing is a Java technology for developing

desktop applications that can run on various platforms such as Windows, Linux, Mac OS X and Solaris. An IDE is a programming scope that is integrated into a software application that provides a Graphic User Interface (GUI), a code or text editor, a compiler and a debugger. NetBeans refers to both a platform framework for Java desktop applications, and an integrated development environment (IDE) for development with Java, JavaScript, PHP, Python, Ruby, Groovy, C, C ++, Scala, Clojure, and others [11].

B. Metadata Standard

There are several types of file metadata, including descriptive metadata, which is data that can identify sources of information so that it can be used to facilitate the discovery and selection process. The scope of this data is the author, title, year of publication, subject title or keywords and other information whose data filling process is the same as a traditional catalog. Administrative metadata is data that can not only identify the source of information but also how it is managed. The scope of this data is the same as descriptive data except that it is added with the data generator, creation time, file type, and other technical data. In addition, this data also contains information about access rights, intellectual property rights, storage and preservation of information sources. Structural metadata is data that can make related data relate to one another. More clearly, this metadata is used to determine the relationship between physical files and pages, pages and chapters and chapters with books as the final product [12].

Several standards are used in making spatial metadata, namely: FGDC, ISO 19115, Dublin Core and SNI Metadata. The ISO 19115/19139 metadata standard is a standard for generating metadata for geospatial data. The ISO 19115 format is the international standard for geographic information metadata and the ISO 19139 format is an implementation scheme for ISO 19115. ISO 19115 has 409 elements and there are 22 core elements needed to describe data and has compound elements under it. The role is divided into 11 main components, namely identification, boundaries, data quality, spatial representation, reference systems, data information, catalog portal references, distribution, additional information and application scheme information (ISO, 2003). ISO 19139 schema is used to describe, validate and exchange geospatial metadata prepared in XML (Extensible Markup Language) format [13].

C. Digital Evidence

In an investigation, the existence of evidence is very important for the continuity of the case being investigated, because with the evidence, an analysis will be carried out to reveal the motives and perpetrators of the crime. The investigators are expected to be able to understand the types of evidence so that when they carry out the investigation process they identify the evidence which is a priority for priority. There are several terms that are almost the same, namely electronic evidence, digital evidence and findings of evidence [14].

The findings of evidence are digital evidence which is more meaningful as output analysis obtained by investigators which leads directly to the reconstruction of the case at hand. In this case, digital evidence is information that is directly related to the data required by the investigator in the investigation process [15].

D. File

Files are data that is on the computer. Any data on a computer can be categorized as a file. Files are not only limited to certain data. Every data, be it image data, numeric data, word data, video data, voice data, application data, and other data is a file. Files are data stored in media that have information on file size, date and time of file storage, file names, file characteristics (characteristics of the application that created them) and file attributes [16].

The forensic metadata system design that has been built can read all types of file types on the computer, such as document files with DOCX extension, ebook files with PDF extension, image files with JPG extension, audio files with MP3 extension, video files with MP4 extension, acquisition files with DD extension, imaging files with E01 extension and other files [17].

E. Correlation File

Correlation can be interpreted as a relationship. However, when developed further, correlation can not only be understood as such. Correlation is one of the analytical techniques in statistics used to find a relationship between two quantitative variables. The relationship between these two variables can occur because of a causal relationship or it can also occur by chance. Two variables are said to be correlated if changes in one variable will be followed by changes in the other variable regularly in the same or opposite direction [18].

In testing this method, there are four types of metadata correlation which are used as examples, namely metadata file date, size, file type and owner. An investigator can search for all types of files that are on the computer based on these four correlation options.

IV. RESEARCH METHODS

The method used in forensic metadata research to analyze the content of digital evidence can be seen in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1. Research Methodology

Based on Figure 1 above the research methodology that will be built is broadly divided into three stages, namely the first stage consisting of problem identification and literature review, the second stage or the design and testing stages of tools consisting of data collection methods, system requirements analysis, system design, implementation system and testing tools as well as the last stage, namely the completion stage in the form of analysis of results and conclusions containing the preparation of research reports.

To further clarify and explain in its entirety all stages of the research that will be carried out, you can also see the research fishbone diagram in Figure 2 below:

Figure 2. Fishbone Research Diagram

V. ANALYSIS AND RESULT

A. Needs Analysis

To make it easier to analyze a system, two types of requirements are needed. Functional needs and non-functional requirements. Functional requirements are needs that contain what processes the system will carry out, while non-functional requirements are those that focus on the behavioral properties of the system..

The functional requirements in the design of this forensic metadata system are as follows:

1. This system design is able to view the metadata of all file types.
2. The system design is also capable of designing an algorithm method to perform metadata correlation parameters based on file types.

Non-functional requirements, which consist of the hardware and software used in building and testing the forensic metadata system design, are as follows:

1. Windows 10 Operating System
2. Netbeans IDE 8.2 compiler for Java programming
3. All types of files on the computer, such as TXT, DOCX, PDF, JPG, RAR, HTML, MP3, MP4, DD, E01 and others
4. Intel Core i5 CPU
5. Memory 4 GB
6. Hard Disk 1000 GB / 1 TB
7. Monitor with 1024 x 600 Pixel Resolution
8. Keyboard and Mouse

B. System Design

The method used to build a system or method of this forensic metadata algorithm is by using a structured design method and using a Workflow (Work Chart) and Flowchart (Flowchart). This design starts from a general design called a conceptual design or logical design. The result of this stage is an essential form of the model, which is what the system must

do to implement it. Then the system design is proceeded to a detailed design.

The general design flow of the forensic metadata system design can be seen in Figure 3 below:

Figure 3. Flow of Forensic Metadata System Design

Explanation of the 3-flow drawing of the general design of the forensic metadata system:

1. An investigator or digital forensic expert will examine computers / laptops that are suspected of being used as a crime related to the types of files or data contained in the computer / laptop.
2. The investigator will first turn on a computer / laptop.
3. There are many types of document files on the computer / laptop.
4. Metadata files that will be read are files on the computer such as files with extensions DOCX, PDF, JPG, MP3, MP4, DD, E01 and others.
5. Next, the investigator will read the metadata using a forensic metadata system or algorithm that has been built.
6. After the metadata file has been read, an investigator will then conduct an investigation or analysis of the metadata.
7. After the analysis is carried out, the investigator then correlates the metadata files based on the parameters of the Metadata File Date, File Size, File Type and File Owner by using a system or forensic metadata algorithm that has been built.
8. Found several files related to the parameters that have been input.
9. After what is found from the correlation, then it is analyzed first before reporting.
10. Reports from the results of the forensic metadata system.

C. System Testing

At this stage the forensic metadata system testing is carried out which aims to detect software failures so that system errors can be found and corrected. Software testing is an investigation carried out to obtain information about the quality of the product or service being tested.

In this research, we need a computer / laptop that contains files for the testing process. The system testing process is carried out in two stages, where each stage is as follows:

1. The first stage is the testing process carried out to read or understand the characteristics of the metadata files in a forensic metadata system or algorithm which is described in the following flowchart flowchart:

Figure 4. Flowchart of File Metadata Reading Testing

First, start or run the system, then input the files that will be read or the metadata is recognized, where the files to be read are files with extensions docx, pdf, jpg, mp3, mp4, dd, e01 and other file, then the program will processing files that have been inputted, there is a condition, where the unreadable file metadata will return to the input file object, but the readable file metadata will immediately display the file metadata, then an analysis / investigation is carried out on the file metadata that has been read and last program is closed or finished running.

2. The second stage is the testing process carried out for file metadata correlation based on parameters that have been set in a forensic metadata system or algorithm which is described in the following flowchart flowchart:

Figure 5. Flowchart of File Metadata Correlation Testing

First, start or the system that has been run is just waiting for the command to start again, inputting the location of the correlation first (Data C, Data D or Data E) or the Folder Path on the computer, then selecting the metadata file based on the correlation parameters from File Date, File Size, File Type and File Owner, then the system will carry out the process of finding the correlation of metadata files that have been created, there are statements or conditions where there are many files, if the files are still not found correlation metadata then the system will again select The file metadata correlation option is as usual, but if the files have been found from the file metadata correlation based on the parameters that have been built, it will proceed to the analysis / investigation of the files that have been found, and finally this system is finished being used and closed.

D. System Implementation

The implementation of the forensic metadata system design program when it is just running will display the Main File Menu (to find the main file to be browsed) and the Metadata Detail Menu (which includes the General Menu to view file metadata in general and the Details Menu to view more file metadata. more specifically), then when the next menu selects the Metadata Correlation Menu (which will determine the location where to search for files and file correlation options from four kinds of file metadata parameters, namely date, size, file extension and file owner name) and Correlation Results Menu reserved space for files that have been found, based on a selection from the file correlation menu that has been specified).

The following is the implementation of the program when it is just running, as shown in Figure 4 below:

Figure 6. Implementation of File Metadata Menu Program

E. Perform Testing and Analysis of Results

Search and View Metadata File

The file that will be read the metadata, will first be browsed or searched for a file on the computer, after which the program will process the file until the metadata is identified one by one, then the metadata description will be displayed in the metadata detail table, like we are trying to browse a file from the acquisition of Imaging.E01 which is in

the Imaging Process Folder in Data D, the results are as shown in Figure 7 and Figure 8 below:

Figure 7. Metadata of General

In Figure 7 Metadata of General, you can find general metadata files that have been inputted before, where File Location: (located at) D: \ ProcessImaging \ Imaging.E01, File Name: (is) Imaging.E01, Extension / File Type: (is) E01, Owner: (is) Administrators and Computer: (is) DESKTOP-H1C8GI7.

Figure 8. Metadata of Detail

In Figure 8 Metadata of Detail, a more detailed metadata file is also found in the previously inputted file, where CreationTime: (is) 2017-01-16T15: 43: 40.929069Z, LastAccessTime: (was) 2017-01-16T15: 43 : 40.929069Z, LastModifiedTime: (was) 2017-01-16T15: 48: 08.291819Z, IsDirectory: (was) false, IsOther: (was) false, IsRegularFile: (was) true, IsSymbolicLink: (was) false and Size: (of) 3718986211byte.

Performs Metadata Correlation Parameters Based On File Type

To correlate file metadata, four types of correlation have been made, namely file metadata date, size, file type and owner. The following tests were carried out using these four types of correlation.

1. Correlation Based on Date

If one of them has been selected, for example the date and click the file option you want to appear, is the date bigger than the Welcome.docx file that was already browsed, then click the File Correlation button, then the files in Data D

are the date is greater than the Welcome.docx file. This forensic metadata system will immediately search for this forensic metadata system, after waiting for a while, you will find a lot of files in the folders in Data D and the results are as shown below:

Figure 9. Correlation with File Date

For the results of the correlated file metadata, namely the Welcome.docx file whose date metadata is “April 27, 2016”, a search was carried out for files located in Data D with the option “Larger”, so there were many files with a larger date. April 27, 2016, from the metadata of the Welcome.docx file date in Data D, but from the many files that have been found, five samples were taken to be used as file search analysis based on date correlation. The following can be seen from the results of the analysis from table 1 below:

Table 1. File Date Correlation Results

No	File Name	Size	Date	Path
1	COVER.doc	91648	28 Oktober 2016	D:\COVER.doc
2	File	38	08 September 2016	D:\File
3	File Backup.txt	26666	03 Januari 2017	D:\File Backup.txt
4	logging.log	7	05 September 2016	D:\logging.log
5	metadata.php	261	10 September 2016	D:\metadata.php

2. Correlation Based on Size

Same as above, if the file size is selected, and the option that appears is smaller than the Welcome.docx file that was browsed, then click the File Correlation button, then the files in Data D are The size is smaller than the Welcome.docx file. This forensic metadata system will immediately search for this forensic metadata system, then wait a few moments, then you will find lots of files in the folders in Data D and the results are as shown below:

Figure 10. Correlation with File Size

For the results of the correlated metadata file, namely the Welcome.docx file whose file size metadata is “10,313 bytes”, a search was carried out for files located in Data E with the option “Smaller”, so there were many files with larger file sizes 10,313 bytes of the welcome.docx file size metadata in Data E, but from the many files that have been found, five samples were taken which were used as file search analysis based on file size correlation. The following can be seen from the results of the analysis from table 2 below:

Table 2. File Size Correlation Results

No	File Name	Size	Date	Path
1	desktop.ini	129	23 November 2015	E:\\$RECYCLE.BIN\S-1-5-21-316737675-2236937756-87291139-1001\desktop.ini
2	digiquran.gif	2052	21 November 2006	E:\AGAMA\Keluarga Islami\Keluarga Sakinah_files\digiquran.gif
3	frames.js	3098	21 November 2006	E:\AGAMA\Keluarga Islami\Keluarga Sakinah_files\frames.js
4	online.gif	1102	21 November 2006	E:\AGAMA\Keluarga Islami\Keluarga Sakinah_files\online.gif
5	top_bar.jpg	589	21 November 2006	E:\AGAMA\Keluarga Islami\Keluarga Sakinah_files\top_bar.jpg

3. Correlation Based on Extension

To see search results based on file extension correlation, select the location of the correlation first, for example in Data E and the File Type option is immediately selected, then the Welcome.docx file that has been browsed with the .docx extension will be immediately searched for by the forensic metadata system, after waiting a few moments, you will find lots of docx files in the folders in Data E and the results are as shown below:

Figure 11. Correlation with File Extension

For the results of the correlated metadata file, namely the Welcome.docx file whose file extension metadata is in the form of “docx”, a search for files located in Data E with the File Type option was found, so many files were found with the file extension docx from the metadata file. type Welcome.docx in Data E, but from the many files that have been found, five samples were taken which were used as file search analysis based on file type correlation. The following can be seen from the results of the analysis from table 3 below:

Table 3. File Extension Correlation Results

No	File Name	Size	Date	Path
1	Fungsi Tombol Pada Keyboard.docx	44725	30 April 2016	E:\ASM Mataram 2016\Fungsi Tombol Pada Keyboard.docx
2	VLOOKUP dan HLOOKUP.docx	161683	07 Mei 2016	E:\ASM Mataram 2016\VLOOKUP dan HLOOKUP.docx
3	409875558039646.docx	8691	17 September 2016	E:\Backup Android\Telegram\Telegram Documents\409875558039646.docx
4	KALDIK TH. 2014-2015 LOBAR.docx	69002	13 Juni 2014	E:\Bahan Pembinaan Gugus Sekotong\KALDIK TH. 2014-2015 LOBAR.docx
4	Kalender Pendidikan.docx	12321	25 Agustus 2014	E:\Bahan Pembinaan Gugus Sekotong\Kalender Pendidikan.docx

4. Correlation by Owner

Next, to see the search results based on the correlation of the file owner, which is to select the location of the correlation first, for example in Documents in Data C and the Owner option is immediately selected, then the Welcome.docx file that was previously browsed whose file owner is named Amikom will be searched for by the system immediately This forensic metadata, then waits for a while, you will find lots of files on behalf of Amikom owners that are in folders in Documents Data C and the results can be seen as shown below:

Figure 12. Correlation with File Owner

For the results of the correlated metadata file, namely the Welcome.docx file whose owner or file owner metadata is “Amikom”, a search for files located in Data D with the Owner option was found. from the Welcome.docx file owner metadata in Data D, but from the many files that have been found, five samples were taken which were used as file search analysis based on file owner correlation. The following can be seen from the results of the analysis from table 4 below:

Table 4. File Owner Correlation Results

No	File Name	Size	Date	Path
1	Tugas CHFI.docx	706260	27 Mei 2016	D:\\$2 UUI\Tugas CHFI.docx
2	Laporan Visualisasi Data.docx	2145635	14 Januari 2016	D:\\$2 UUI\Semester I\Visualisasi Data BI\Laporan Visualisasi Data.docx
3	Laporan Visualisasi Data.docx	2868488	14 Januari 2016	D:\\$2 UUI\Semester I\Laporan Visualisasi Data.docx
4	Pelengkap Laporan.docx	13160	18 Januari 2016	D:\\$2 UUI\Semester III\Olah TKP\Ex UAS Laporan Olah TKP\Pelengkap Laporan.docx
5	Laporan Olah TKP.docx	4448169	31 Januari 2016	D:\\$2 UUI\Semester III\Olah TKP\Laporan FINAL O-TKP\Laporan Olah TKP.docx

VI. CONCLUSION

The design of the forensic metadata system is very much needed by interested people, especially law enforcers in the Republic in uncovering a case related to the process of investigating digital evidence. So from the results of this study several conclusions can be drawn, namely as follows. The forensic metadata system design application can see all types of metadata files that are on the computer and there are no restrictions on certain files that the file metadata cannot be seen. Visible file metadata are general file metadata and more specific file metadata. For example, you can see File Location, File Name, File Type, Owner Computer, Creation Time, Last Access Time, Last Modified Time, Directory, Other, Regular File, Symbolic Link and Size. You can find files on your computer from correlation search results based on certain parameters of existing file metadata types such as Metadata File Date, Size, File Type and Owner.

VII. FUTURE WORK

In the implementation of this research, there are several obstacles faced by the author, especially the limited insight in the making of a forensic metadata system design application, so there is a lot that needs to be explored more deeply so that in the future the theme of this research is more perfect, as suggested by the following authors. The view of file metadata that can be found is still limited and not too much, because as we know that files store many types of metadata. File metadata correlations that are used as parameters can go deeper and deeper in performing several types of file searches. For future research related to forensic metadata, this is not only limited to looking at file metadata in general but can also see which file metadata has changed based on the time of the change.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Raghavan and S. V. Raghavan, "AssocGEN: Engine for analyzing metadata based associations in digital evidence," *Int. Work. Syst. Approaches Digit. Forensics Eng.*, SADFE, 2014.
- [2] Niso. (2004). *Understanding Metadata*: NISO Press. Retrieved from www.niso.org
- [3] Pendit, Putu Laxman. (2007). *Perpustakaan Digital: Perspektif Perpustakaan Perguruan Tinggi Indonesia*. Jakarta: Sagung Seto
- [4] Technical Working Group Clearinghouse. (2005). *Panduan Pembangunan Metadata Spasial*. Marine and Coastal Resources Management Project: Bakosurtanal
- [5] Sriram Raghavan & S V Raghavan. (2013). *AssocGEN: Engine for Analyzing Metadata Based Associations in Digital Evidence*. IEEE Louisville Chapter. 978-1-4799-4061-5/13.
- [6] L. Drive, M. Hall, C. Hill, K. Woods, A. Chassanoff, and C. a Lee, "Managing and Transforming Digital Forensics Metadata for Digital Collections," *10th Int. Conf. Preserv. Digit. Objects*, no. November, pp. 203–208, 2013.
- [7] S. Raghavan and S. V Raghavan, "A study of forensic & analysis tools," *2013 8th Int. Work. Syst. Approaches to Digit. Forensics Eng.*, pp. 1–5, 2013.
- [8] Ezz El-Din Hemdan & Manjaiah D.H. (2015). *Forensic Analysis Approach Based on Metadata and Hash Values for Digital Objects in the Cloud*. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Computer and Communication Engineering*. Vol. 3, Special Issue 7, October 2015.
- [9] A. Spore, "Report Information from ProQuest," no. June, 2016.
- [10] 4. P. R. Kumar, C. Srikanth, and K. L. Sailaja, "Location Identification of the Individual based on Image Metadata," *Procedia Comput. Sci.*, vol. 85, no. Cms, pp. 451–454, 2016.
- [11] 8. R. Sharma and S. Koshy, "Promoting Open Source Technology in Education : NetBeans : The Perfect Open Source IDE," vol. 4333, pp. 571–575, 2011.
- [12] U. Salama, V. Varadharajan, M. Hitchens, and DUMMY, "Metadata Based Forensic Analysis of Digital Information in the Web," *Annu. Symp. Inf. Assur. Secur. Knowl. Manag.*, pp. 9–15, 2012.
- [13] Silviana, Arlis, Rita., & Mahendra, Saputra, Riyan. (2014). *PENGEMBANGAN MODUL KONVERSI METADATA SPOT 5 VIRTUAL RECEPTION SESUAI FORMAT ISO 19115/19139*: Seminar Nasional Penginderaan Jauh 2014
- [14] Wahyudi, Erfan & Riadi, Imam & Prayudi, Yudi. (2018). *Virtual Machine Forensic Analysis And Recovery Method For Recovery And Analysis Digital Evidence*. *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security (IJCSIS)*,. 16.
- [15] Y. Prayudi, 2014 "Problema Dan Solusi Digital Chain Of Custody Dalam Proses Investigasi," April,
- [16] Subli, Moh & Sugiantoro, Bambang & Prayudi, Yudi. (2017). *METADATA FORENSIK UNTUK Mendukung Proses Investigasi Digital*. *Jurnal Ilmiah DASL*. 18.
- [17] Imanda Putra, Alfiansyah & Umar, Rusydi & Fadlil, Abdul. (2018). *ANALISIS FORENSIK DETEKSI KEASLIAN METADATA VIDEO MENGGUNAKAN EXIFTOOL*. *Seminar Nasional Informatika 2018 (semnasIF 2018)*.
- [18] Zaenudin & Sugiantoro, Bambang & Prayudi, Yudi. (2018). *Correlation Analysis Of Forensic Metadata For Digital Evidence*. *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security (IJCSIS)*,. 16.